

brown planthopper was high while methomyl and methyl parathion were ineffective ovicides.

Solutions of the same insecticides and concentrations were tested for larvicidal activity by spraying on 25-day-old TN1 seedlings. One day after treatment, leaves were cut from the seedlings placed in petri dishes with

Activity of certain insecticides at 0.04% concentration on the eggs and larvae of rice leaf folder.^a IRRILaboratory, 1979.

Insecticide	Eggs hatched (%)	Larval mortality (%)
Methyl parathion	0	100
Carbofuran	0	100
Triazophos	0	100
Methomyl	17.5	100
Control	100.0	0

^aAV of 4 replications.

moistened filter paper, and infested with 10 freshly hatched larvae. Forty-eight hours later, living and dead larvae were counted. All larvae on the treated leaves were dead, but those on the control were alive and active (see table). ■

Occurrence of brown and whitebacked planthoppers in Uttar Pradesh, India

S. K. Verma, P. K. Pathak, B. N. Singh, and M. N. Lal, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, India

The presence of brown planthopper (BPH) in Uttar Pradesh was first noticed during 1969 kharif at Pantnagar University farms. Since then, it has infested the crop regularly, except in 1970 when the crop was free of attack. High incidence in most of the years resulted in typical hopperburn.

During a survey in 1977 kharif, BPH was widespread throughout the state. In some places, particularly the tarai region, where the farmers usually grow high yielding varieties with high doses of fertilizers, the attack produced hopperburn at the boot-leaf to hard dough stage of the crop. Varieties Jaya, IR8, IR24, Saket 4, Pusa 2.21, Ratna, and Bala were severely damaged and the BPH populations ranged from 100 to 1,000 per hill in the hopperburned plots.

The weather was warm and humid and the fields had standing irrigated water.

The whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* has also attacked the crop regularly since 1969. However, the degree of infestation varies. Infestation was severe only in 1972 and 1977, when typical hopperburn occurred during the late tillering phase of the crop. In a 1972 trial, the control of the pest resulted in 99% increase in yield. Under field conditions IR20 (in 1972) RP633-510-1-3-4-1, and IR36 (in 1977) showed some resistance. ■

Effects of biocides on brown planthopper adults on rice

P. R. M. Rao and P. S. Prakusa Kao, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack, India

The brown planthopper (BPH) attacks high yielding rices, particularly at the ripening stage. Chemical control of BPH at crop maturity is hazardous because of the possibility of toxic residues in the grain and straw. Therefore, BPH control through the use of the biocides *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Thuricide HP), and aqueous extracts of leaves of neem *Azadirachta indica* and *Eclipta alba* (a weed) was explored at CRRI.

Thirty-day-old TN1 seedlings were

Effectiveness of three biological formulations on brown planthopper adults^a. Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, 11 - 13 April 1977.

Treatments	Mortality (corrected to 1%) at	
	24 h	48 h
<i>Thuricide HP</i>		
0.25 kg/100 liters water	100	100
0.50 kg/100 liters water	100	100
0.75 kg/100 liters water	100	100
1.0 kg/ 100 liters water	100	100
<i>Aqueous extract of Eclipta alba</i>		
Extract of root portion	52	70
Extract of shoot portion	35	70
<i>Aqueous extract of neem</i>		
Hot water neem leaf extract	60	100
Neem leaf extract (1st fraction)	42	62
Neem leaf extract (2d fraction)	30	55
Mortality (%) in control	0	0

^aAv of 4 replications. Max temp = 34.4°C; min temp = 22.2°C; mean max temp = 33.7°C; mean min temp = 24.°C; mean relative humidity = 74%.

transplanted in earthenware pots (15-cm diam). At 40 days, the plants were sprayed with the biocides with a fine atomizer until the runoff stage. The sprayed plants were allowed to dry naturally for 1 hour, then 10 BPH adults were caged in each pot. The treatments were replicated four times with untreated plants as the control. Mortality counts were taken 24 and 48 hours after insect release.

All doses of Thuricide gave 100% BPH mortality (see table). Insect mortality was considerable with both root and shoot extracts of *E. alba* and with neem extracts acquired by different methods. ■

Leaf folder outbreak in tarai and hill regions of Uttar Pradesh, India

S. K. Verma, P. K. Pathak, B. N. Singh, and M. N. Lal, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, India

The leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* Guenee is becoming a common rice pest. The insect's first outbreak in Uttar Pradesh occurred in 1977 kharif at the Pantnagar University farms. A survey in September 1977 showed high populations of the pest not only in the tarai but also in the hilly regions (up to 1.500 m altitude).

As much as 60% of the rice leaves was damaged at the University farms and in some farmers' fields. The population began to appear in the field in July and remained until October, producing four or five generations. The early sown and upland crops suffered heavily. Ekalux 25 EC sprayed at 0.5 kg a.i./ha gave good field control. ■

Whorl maggot damage on flag leaf

S. K. Basu, entomologist, Rice Production Training Institute (RPTI), Hindustan Fertilizer Corporation Ltd, Fertilizer Promotion and Agricultural Research Division, Durgapur 71 3212, India

Whorl maggot *Hydrellia* sp. regularly damages rice at the RPTI farm throughout the year. It often attacks

the entire crop at the seedling stage.

Recently a late-sown 1978 kharif crop of the variety Jaya was attacked after the heading stage. Small punctures

appeared in the middle of the flag leaf and its margin was sometimes discolored. On a few plants, the second and third leaves were also damaged. ■

Evaluation of insecticides for gall midge control

B. C. Shukla, S. K. Shrivastava, P. D. Deshmukh, D. J. Pophali, U. K. Kaushik, G. A. Gangrade, and G. L. Patidar, Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, College of Agriculture, Raipur, India

Large strips of Ratna that had been transplanted on 3 August 1978 were

treated on 8 and 24 September with several insecticides and formulations.

At harvest observations were made on two 1 × 1-m plots in each treatment to determine the percentages of silver shoots and the yield (see table). Percent silver shoots was lowest and yield highest in the granular treatment of quinalphos. ■

Percentage of silver shoots and panicles, and yield of Ratna treated with various insecticides. Raipur, India, 1978.

Treatment	Dosage	Silver shoots (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Quinalphos 5G	1 kg a.i./ha	32.0	2.7
Phorate 10G	1 kg a.i./ha	36.0	2.0
Carbofuran 3G	1 kg a.i./ha	36.7	1.8
Malathion 50EC	0.05% concn	47.6	1.6
Sevimol 40EC	0.05% concn	41.0	2.0
Phosalone 35 EC	0.05% concn	48.3	1.9
Monocrotophos 40 EC	0.05% concn	56.8	1.8
Phosphamidon 100EC	0.05% concn	33.9	1.6
Quinalphos 30EC	0.05% concn	40.2	1.5
BHC 10% dust	25 kg/ha	41.4	1.5
Untreated control	—	69.0	1.5

^aCarbaryl in molasses.

Biological studies of the population dynamics of rice brown planthopper and green leafhopper

P. Narayanasamy, B. Balusubramanian, and P. Baskaran, Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, Annamalai University, Annamalaiagar, Tamil Nadu, India

The influence of weather factors on the field populations of rice brown planthopper (BPH) and green leafhopper (GLH) was studied.

GLH populations increased at both

higher maximum and minimum temperatures (see table). BPH populations decreased at both high temperatures and lower minimum temperatures. GLH populations were higher at lower humidity levels. but BPH populations were positively correlated with higher humidity. No direct relationship between the amount of rainfall and GLH incidence was found. But the BPH population peaked at no or low rainfall (6-10 mm) and declined when rainfall exceeded 10 mm.

Correlation between weather elements and the incidence of rice green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers, Annamalaiagar, India.^a

Weather element	Green leafhopper		Brown planthopper (short-term season)
	Short term (Jul-Sep)	2d season (Nov-Jan)	
Max temp	+0.7166**	+0.5030*	-0.8122**
Min temp	-0.6922**	-0.5021*	+0.9122**
Humidity	-0.7022**	-0.7790**	+0.5610**
Rainfall	0.0056 ns	1.1450 ns	-0.7101**
Sunshine	+0.6328*	+0.7516**	-0.6222**

^a* Significant at 5% level. ** Significant at 1% level. ns = not significant.

The GLH population was higher with more bright sunshine (3-8 hours) and decreased with fewer hours of sunshine. The BPH population increased with fewer bright-sunshine hours. ■

Rice leaf folder attacks in India

P. B. Chatterjee, Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, Pandua 712149, Hooghly, India

The rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), normally a minor rice pest, occurred in epidemic proportions in 1978 on upland, drilled autumn rice (aus) in Coochbehar and Jalpaiguri, two rice-growing districts of North Bengal, India. Most areas of maximum infestation were on the peripheral regions of forest reserves and on plains near the foothills of the sub-Himalayan ranges. In aus rice, which is generally sown in March or April and harvested in July or August, the infestation was first noticed in the last week of April; incidence peaked in the second week of May. The insect spread to about 22,000 ha. Where infestation was severe, the rice plants (almost entirely rainfed) withered completely. Coochbehar and Jalpaiguri receive an average annual precipitation of about 3,200 mm. Rainfall averages 50, 130, and 400 mm in March, April, and May. But in 1978, it averaged 3.2, 100.2, and 295 mm. The attack was confined mostly to the late-sown crop. But the infestation subsided with the onset of late May rains. ■

Performance of sprayers and influence of water volumes in insecticidal control of rice ear-cutting caterpillar

R. K. Patel, Department of Entomology, J. N. Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India

A field experiment was conducted to test the performance of sprayers and the influence of water volumes in control of the rice ear-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* Walk in paddy at Varansai in 1976-77. The ground sprayers evaluated were mist-blower, hand-compression, foot, and knapsack sprayers. The volumes